

THEORITICAL VIEWS ON THE PHENOMENON OF SYMMETRY AND ASYMMETRY IN WORLD LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical interpretation of symmetrical and asymmetrical phenomena in linguistics and their role in the language system. The study analyzes the relationship between form and content between linguistic units, their compatibility or incompatibility. It is shown that symmetry expresses a balanced, harmonious relationship between form and content in the language system, while asymmetry manifests itself in such phenomena as disproportion, ambiguity, synonymy and homonymy between them.

Key words: symmetry, asymmetry, cognitive activity, concept, dissymmetry.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается теоретическая интерпретация симметричных и асимметричных явлений в лингвистике и их роль в языковой системе. В исследовании анализируется взаимосвязь формы и содержания между языковыми единицами, их совместимость или несовместимость. Показано, что симметрия выражает сбалансированное, гармоничное соотношение формы и содержания в языковой системе, тогда как асимметрия проявляется в таких явлениях, как диспропорция, двусмысленность, синонимия и омонимия между ними.

Ключевые слова: симметрия, асимметрия, познавательная деятельность, понятие, диссимметрия.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tilshunoslikda simmetrik va asimmetrik hodisalarning nazariy talqini hamda ularning til tizimidagi o‘rni yoritiladi. Tadqiqotda til birliklari o‘rtasidagi shakl va mazmun munosabatlari, ularning o‘zaro mosligi yoki nomosligi masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Simmetriya til tizimida shakl va mazmunning muvozanatli, o‘zaro uyg‘un munosabatini ifodalasa, asimmetriya esa ular o‘rtasidagi nomutanosiblik, ko‘pma’ nolilik, sinonimiya va omonimiya kabi hodisalarda namoyon bo‘lishi ko‘rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: simmetriya, asimmetriya, kognitiv faoliyat, konsept, dissimetriya.

Introduction.

Today, linguocognitology, as a type of cognitive activity, contributes to the development and typology of existing general and specific paradigms about human language. Its scope is very wide, covering various modern areas of linguistics, and, if necessary, the history of paradigms in one or another area.

As is known, by the end of the last century, there was a need to reconsider and study linguistic phenomena and related concepts from a new perspective. Regardless of the goals and objectives of various areas of linguistics, their object of study has always been and remains language and speech units.

Symmetry is a general philosophical scientific category that describes the structure of the formation of systems. Initially, this concept was implicitly manifested in the works of ancient Greek philosophers and mathematicians. The main goal was to determine, measure and determine the degree of internal connection, relationships between objects. The concept of symmetry entered physics in the first quarter of the 19th century, chemistry in the second half of the 19th century, and natural science at the end of the 19th century. The systemic nature of linguistic units and linguistic phenomena found its expression in the teachings of F. de Saussure at the beginning of the 20th century. This doctrine can be recognized as the first serious scientific theory of language symmetry. However, if we take as a basis the idea that the systemic nature of language is the composition of its constituent elements, their arrangement, and also that systemic relations are manifested differently in different areas of language, it becomes clear that the concepts of symmetry-asymmetry are not a new phenomenon for

Main part. Thoughts on the theory of symmetrical concepts are reflected in the works of Academician A.V. Shubnikov, who gives the following general definition of symmetry of uniformity: “In a broad sense, under an asymmetric form we understand a form consisting of parts located equally and unequally relative to each other”⁴⁰. Or “symmetry is defined as “a law of the structure of structural objects, or more precisely, a group of permissible changes that preserve the structural integrity of the systems under consideration”.

Equality, correspondence between objects and phenomena acquires relativity in a broad sense. If two objects and phenomena are similar in a certain characteristic, property, they are considered equal. For example, rooms under the same roof may be the same height, but their size, color, structure and quality may differ from each other. This is also characteristic of linguistic units. For example, the lexeme “eye” represents the organ of vision and may be similar or different in certain life and speech situations in the languages of the world according to its location, size, color, movement and function. Therefore, when the similarity, correspondence between objects and phenomena of the same category is violated, the phenomenon of asymmetry occurs.

In scientific research processes, it is important to distinguish between symmetrical and asymmetrical states. If a material or immaterial event or phenomenon related to a particular area of scientific thought does not have its characteristic features, this state can be called asymmetry. In other words, when we say the phenomenon of asymmetry, we mean the absence or violation of symmetry elements. Therefore, in scientific observation and scientific analysis, it is necessary to study these two phenomena in the same status. Because, we believe that scientific phenomena and concepts about a particular object of research will be complete and perfect only if we take into account both their symmetry and asymmetry. In this case, we believe that asymmetry should be interpreted not as an abnormal state, but as part of the existing knowledge about phenomena, their characteristics.

To summarize from the above, the concepts of symmetry and asymmetry are also phenomena inherent in language, and they are a number of important features such as stability, variability, order and its violation, semantic and formal compatibility and incompatibility, functional compatibility and its degrees. For example, in English, there are asymmetrical, symmetrical cases between personal forms of verbs and modal verbs, impersonal forms of verbs. In general, the following symmetrical cases are observed among them:

- 1) it is a nominative unit expressing an action or state;
- 2) it has the categories of tense, person, number, mood, aspect;
- 3) it appears in the structure of a sentence as a component of predicative (possessive, participial) relations, has a simple and complex structure;
- 4) it performs various syntactic functions in the structure of a sentence, etc.

The following asymmetric cases are observed in verbs in English:

1. The characteristic of modal verbs is not to express an action or state, but to express a subjective attitude towards its implementation.

2. Modal verbs do not have certain categories (person, number, etc.) characteristic of verbs, or defective cases in expressing certain specific grammatical categories (tense, mood), or symmetrical and deviating or exceptional cases in expressing the plural category in words belonging to the noun class are examples of asymmetry. For example, if the formation of plurals in nouns with the addition of -s (-es), -en is considered a symmetrical situation, then the vowels in the noun or the change of the word to another form (a mouse – mice, a tooth – teeth), the mixing of symmetrical and asymmetrical forms (a leaf – leaves, a calve – calves), or the fact that the singular and plural forms are the same, in some nouns this category is expressed at levels above the lexical level (a piece/pieces of information, advice), etc. can be examples of asymmetry. The above represents the general situation of asymmetry. A more precise approach to this issue provides concrete, complete knowledge and ideas on the issue under consideration.

In our opinion, the laws of symmetry in language can cause asymmetry in some specific cases. This situation can be caused by the knowledge, level of competence of the communicating persons, the absence of a certain life, speech situation. This is seen, for example, in the interpretation of the following sentences: *I need two hands* (in the sense of the hands of the clock); *I need two assistants* (in

³⁹ Карцевский С.О. Большая советская энциклопедия: [в 30 т.] / под ред. А.М. Прохорова. – 3-е изд. – Москва: Советская энциклопедия, 1969.

⁴⁰ Шубников А.В., Копчик В.А. Симметрия в науке и искусстве. – Москва-Ижевск: Институт компьютерных исследований, 2012. – С. 261.

the sense of the stage masters) or *We have two eyes there* (1) We have two scouts there. 2) We have two spies (stalkers) there).

In this regard, knowledge about the degrees of symmetry is also important. From this point of view, it is probably appropriate to distinguish between complete and (partially complete) and incorrect forms of symmetry. In this study, the role of the mental linguistic model of the concept of "wealth" is played by a certain structure of knowledge combined with the state cognitotype, that is, the concept of "poor". The aim of the study is to objectify the content of the concepts of "wealth\poverty" in the minds of Uzbek and English linguists and to identify the semantic structure of this concept and its elements.

Symmetry is observed in the living and non-living nature that surrounds us, in man-made objects, in various fields of knowledge (biology, chemistry, mathematics, and language), in fiction, and so on. It follows that we live in a world of symmetry. The world of plants, flowers, animals, birds, worms, and humans all live and develop according to the laws of symmetry.

Tirik va notirik olamdagi obyektlar va ularga xos umumiy va o‘xshash xususiyat va vazifalardan chetlashish ular o‘rtasidagi simmetriyaning so‘nib borishiga va asimmetrik holat yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo‘ladi.

The phenomenon of asymmetry is interpreted differently by scientists and experts in different fields. For example, asymmetry is the absence of symmetry or the violation of symmetry. In the “Novaya filosofskaya ensiklopediya”, asymmetry is defined as "the absence of elements of symmetry in natural and theoretical objects".

To make it more descriptive, we will try to illustrate the phenomenon of asymmetry with the example of linguistic phenomena. The phenomenon of asymmetry can be complete and incomplete. The first category is seen in the asymmetric state of a word group, for example, in the differences between verbs denoting action-state and modal verbs.

While verbs denoting action-state express corresponding actions and states in objective reality, modal verbs do not have this property. Their main function is to express a subjective attitude towards those actions and states. The asymmetric state is also observed in the way English verbs express these actions-states in existence and subjective attitudes towards them in the language.

Examples of complete asymmetry between languages include the absence of modal verbs in Uzbek and Russian, the absence of grammatical gender categories in nouns in English and Uzbek, the presence or absence of objects in Russian and German, and the absence of some words in English and German.

False asymmetry (or dissymmetry) refers to the weakening (reduction) of the state of symmetry in a language or between languages, that is, the absence of some elements of linguistic units. For example, the presence of nouns that are used only in the singular in English and Uzbek, or in English only in the plural: *bolalik, mardlik, ko‘mir, havo, suv; advice, progress, information, sheep, air, salt, trousers, spectacles*. The absence of an indefinite form in the five definite relative forms of continuous verbs (*will be writing, has been writing, had been writing, will have been writing, to be writing*).

Examples of false asymmetry include the fact that nouns that denote the concentration, wholeness, and generality of objects in the Uzbek language (childhood, friendship, wheat, flour, oil) denote many objects considered as a whole in the singular form, the differences between the number of conjugations in nouns in English and Uzbek (2\6) and their means of expression, the fact that nouns in the genitive conjugation in English, Uzbek, and other languages do not have conjugation markers, complete symmetry, the absence of a sign of the accusative case in Uzbek (in the land of the people (proverb), functional or stylistic differences between units expressing causation in English, etc.

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